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**REVIEW OF THE INHIBITIVE EFFECT OF *CANNABIS SATIVA* IN DIFFERENT METAL AND
CORROSIVE ENVIRONMENTS**

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of the study is to summarize and analyze previous research work that the extract of cannabis sativa act as a good, eco-friendly and reliable corrosion inhibitor in different corrosive environment and like mild steel, aluminium, brass and zinc. Findings from previous investigations indicate that inhibition efficiency increases with higher extract concentration, and the adsorption behaviour of the extract follows the Langmuir adsorption isotherm. While increase in extract decreases the corrosion rate and increase in acid concentration lower the inhibition as reported by previous researched. All corrosion measuring techniques used in previous investigations proved the effectiveness of the extract as good corrosion inhibitor.

Keywords: Marijuana, Corrosion, Inhibitor, Extract, Efficiency, Adsorption

INTRODUCTION

Corrosion in simple terms occurs in metals because most metals are not in their natural state until they return to the ore form in which we found them. Almost all metals are found as an oxide, sulfide or some other metal compound. Only few metals such as gold occur in nature in the metallic form. Thus, all metals that are derived from ores want to return to that form and corrosion is the reaction process that allows this return to nature to occur (Budinski, 1979; Abdallah 2004). In the case of plastics and ceramics, the return to nature is not so apparent. Corrosion occurs in plastics because plastic can be affected by various environments. Plastics do not rust. Deterioration is due to loss of properties (Budinski, 1979; Abdallah, 2004 & Erunoso, 2011). Some specific corrosion types are: uniform, atmospheric, pitting, intergranular, stress, fatigue, fretting, erosion or impingement, cavitation, crevice, microbiological corrosion (Khanna, 2013). Different techniques of corrosion control and prevention are: use of alloy additions, inhibitors, use of high purity metals, environment control, cathodic protection, design against corrosion, special heat-treatment, protective surface coatings (Khanna, 2013).

Inhibitors can be used to control corrosion by altering the environment. They are physically added to a corrodent, usually in small concentration. Inhibitors can be complex compounds, sulfites, chromates, alcohols, polar nitrogen compounds and even salts of such metals as arsenic and antimony (Erunoso, 2011). Inhibitors work in different ways. Often the corroding species in water systems is oxygen; remove the oxygen and you lower corrosion. Some inhibitors, called absorptive inhibitors, attack the rate-controlling steps in the electrochemical corrosion cell. They slow down anode or cathode reactions and thus

slow down the entire corrosion process. Other inhibitors work by making passivation easier. They help to establish the passive film that many metals depend on for corrosion protection (Abdallah, 2004 & Erunoso, 2011). Eddy & Ebenso (2008) reported that Plant extracts used as corrosion inhibitors are eco-friendly, renewable, inexpensive, reliable, and available. phytochemical constituents of plant extract, such as saponnin, tannin, alkaloid, glycoside, amino acid, organic acid, pigments, anthraquinone and flavanoid are the phytochemical constituents of plant extract that determine it inhibition efficiency. Research work were carried out by researchers to investigate the inhibition efficiency of plants and the adsorption kinetics of the extracts on the metal surface and they were found effective (Nwigwe et al 2021; Kolo et al 2018).

Cannabis sativa, more commonly known as marijuana or hemp, is an annual herbaceous flowering plant. It's scientifically classified as *Cannabis sativa*, with 'sativa' meaning 'cultivated'. While often associated with recreational drug use, it also has various uses including food, fiber, building materials and more. Some of its physiochemical properties that enable it to inhibit corrosion are flavonoids, alkaloids, nitrogenated complexes, amino acids etc (Wikipedia). Corrosion rate are measured using the following methods: weight loss (WL) measurements, Tafel exploration, hydrogen penetration, electrochemical corrosion testing methods (EM) etc.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Corrosion is the degradation of metals, concrete, plastics, including wood. Deterioration is often in the form of a loss of properties. Inorganic inhibitors like lead compounds, Chromate, nitrides, phosphates and benzoates are costly, harmful, toxic and with negative environmental effect. Due to its ease of fabrication, workability, availability and low cost, mild steel is mostly use in industry. It corrodes as a result of it contact with acid solutions during acid cleaning, storage, and other chemical processes. Cannabis are wrongly use by smokers and if utilize as corrosion inhibitor it will help in addressing corrosion effect on metal.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this work is to summarize and analyze previous research work that show the effectiveness of extract of *cannabis sativa* as a good, eco-friendly and reliable corrosion inhibitor in different corrosive environment and metals.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. to find out the inhibitive efficiency of cannabis sativa on metal in corrosive environment from previous research work.
- ii. to determine the adsorption kinetics of the extracts on the metal surface from previous investigations.
- iii. to find out from previous studies, the effect of concentration of the extract on the inhibition efficiency of the extract.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research aims to address the following research questions:

- i. What is the inhibition efficiency of marijuana extract in different corrosive environment and metals?
- ii. What is the adsorption kinetic of the extract on metal surface?
- iii. Can the concentration of extract affect inhibition efficiency of extract?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several works were carried out by researchers on plants extract as reliable, available, ecofriendly, cheap and non-toxic methods of corrosion with positive result: Harry et al (2023) reported the effectiveness of tobacco extract in H₂S-

containing NaCl solution in mitigating corrosion of mild steel; Loto and Popoola (2012) investigated the electrochemical Potential Monitoring of Corrosion and Inhibitors Protection of Mild Steel Embedded in Concrete in NaCl Solution; Omotosho et al (2012) study corrosion of low carbon steel in 2 M Sulphuric acid using *Chromolaena odorata*; Kolo et al (2018) determined corrosion inhibition potential of ethanol extract of *Bryophyllum pinnatum* leaves for zinc in acidic medium; Kaya (2023) reported the use of methanol extract of *Rheum Ribes* (İşgin) flower as a natural and promising anti-corrosive agent in acidic solution. Other researched worked on green inhibitors were performed by: Nwigwe et al (2021), studied inhibition efficiency of carica papaya leaf in Microbiologically Induced Corrosion in Fresh-Water Environment. Yong et al (2017) investigated tobacco rob water extract (TRE) as corrosion inhibitor in acid; Fouda et al (2014) determine anti-corrosiveness of Tobacco Plant Extracts of steel. Zheng and Wang (2021) experimented on corrosion inhibition effect of *Cannabis sativa* leaves extracts in acidic medium. As well studies were carried out by Baruku et al (2018) reported Inhibition of Aluminium Corrosion Using Carica papaya Leaves Extract in 1.0 M H₂SO₄.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Many researchers carried out research on the anticorrosive effect of *cannabis sativa* on metal and its alloy. Below are some of the work and results obtained through investigations by researchers:

Zheng and Wang (2021) worked on *Cannabis sativa* leaves extracts on N80 steel in 15% HCl solution as inhibitor for prevention of corrosion. Potentiodynamic polarization techniques analysis result suggests that the extract acts as good inhibitor (mixed type). Result of weight loss reveals the maximum inhibition efficiency value of 97.53% at g/L. Thermodynamic and adsorption properties of the extract obeys Langmuir isotherm model. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) suggests smooth surface of N80 steel with the addition of extract. The Molecular dynamic simulation (MD) results suggest the higher value of adsorption energy for protonated form as compared to neutral form.

Salima et. al. (2024) determined inhibitive ability of marijuana extract on low carbon steel using weight loss and electrochemical corrosion testing methods in acid solution. Different extraction methods were carried out and it yield a maximum inhibition efficiency of 91%. Both experimental and simulation results showed that adsorption kinetics of the extracts on the metal surface fit into Langmuir isotherm. This experiment revealed the extract act as good inhibitor which protect steel from corrosion effect.

Mohamed et. al. (2022) studied the effect of hemp (marijuana) as a reliable corrosion inhibitor for E24 steel in HCl medium: Both experimental and theoretical study were carried out using weight loss method. The result showed that the inhibition effect increased with its concentration, reaching a maximum efficiency of 92%. electrochemical corrosion testing methods reveal the extract act as mixed inhibitor.

Haldhar et. al. (2021) used different corrosion measurement method in his study on marijuana extract for mild steel. Maximum inhibition efficiency of 97.31 % were obtained through electrochemical corrosion testing methods and to know about the thin layer which was formed on the steel for its protection from corrosion. The result showed mixed type inhibitor and the kinetic parameter of activation agreed with Langmuir adsorption. FT-IR technique confirmed the existence of functional groups and the heteroatoms exhibit in the inhibitor. Computational result agreed with the experimental and showed that hemp is a very valuable inhibitor that can be relied on.

Turan et. al. (2020) carried out researched on effectiveness of anticorrosive properties of hemp (marijuana) for Aluminium in sulphuric acid. An excellent percentage (98) of inhibition efficiency were obtained from electrochemical corrosion testing methods. This proved that the extract is a renewable, eco-friendly and reliable inhibitor.

El-Housseiny (2017) studied inhibitive property of cannabis sativa leaves extract on zinc in corrosive environment (H₂SO₄). Flory-Hyggins isotherm, Langmuir and Kinitic-Thermodynamic model were found to be applicable to fit the data of adsorption of cannabis at the Zinc surface. The result showed that the adsorbed species of cannabis extract is an effective inhibitor. The values of Ea and ΔH for dissolution of zinc in acidic medium containing cannabis extract are lower than in its absence indicates a chemisorption mechanism of adsorption.

Israni and Savita (2022) published work on the inhibitive properties and effect of cannabis sativa (dry fruit, leaves and stem extracts) extract on low carbon steel in HCl and H₂SO₄ using mass loss and thermometric methods for different concentration of extract. The outcome of the experiment prove that the extracts performed as a good inhibitor. The fruit extract is more effective than both leaves and stem in inhibiting the corrosion rate of metal in corrosive medium with 92.39% maximum inhibition efficiency. It was observed from the result of the experiment that the inhibition efficiency and corrosion rate were directly proportional to the concentration of extract and concentration of acid solution.

Table 1. Max IE, adsorption isotherms (type of adsorption), type of metal, solution (medium), corrosion measurement methods with References of research done by different author on cannabis sativa (marijuana) extract.

References (Author)	Maximum Inhibition Efficiency	Type of Metal	Corrosive Medium	Corrosion Measurement Methods	Type of adsorption	Extract	Type of inhibitor
Zheng and Wang (2021)	97.53%	N80 steel	HCl	WL and EM	Langmuir	Marijuana	Mixed inhibitor
Salima et al (2024)	91 %,	mild steel	HCl	WL, EIS and PDP	Langmuir	Marijuana	Mixed with a predominantly anodic effect
Mohamed et al (2022)	92%	E24 steel	HCl	WL, EM		Marijuana	Mixed, with a cathodic predominance
Haldhar et al (2021)	97.31%	Low carbon steel	0.5M H ₂ SO ₄	WL, Tafel and EM	Langmuir	Marijuana	
Turan et al (2020)	98%	Aluminium	0.5M H ₂ SO ₄	EM		Marijuana	
El-Housseiny (2017)	Effective	Zinc	0.5M H ₂ SO ₄	EM	Flory-Hyggins	Marijuana	Mixed
Israni and Savita (2022)	92.39%.	Mild steel	HCl and H ₂ SO ₄	WL, Thermometric		Marijuana	

The results obtained by different researcher on the use of marijuana extracts as corrosion inhibitor showed it effectiveness and efficiency in inhibiting corrosion in mild steel, aluminium, zinc and brass. It performed excellently well in some corrosive medium like HCl, sea water, NaCl and H₂SO₄. On inhibition efficiency, the least obtained was 91% by Salima

et al (2024) while the maximum was 98% according to Turan et al (2020). The results obtained from previous work carried out agreed that marijuana extract is an excellent corrosion inhibitor.

Results from all the previous worked on marijuana extract showed that the adsorption kinetics of the extracts on the metal surface fit into Langmuir isotherm except El-Housseiny (2017) that reported Flory-Hyggins type of adsorption. It was observed from previous studies on marijuana extract that concentration of extract and acid solution had great effect on inhibition efficiency and corrosion rate. The higher the concentration of extract the higher the inhibition efficiency and the lower the corrosion rate. The higher the concentration of the acid solution the lower the inhibition efficiency and the higher the corrosion rate. Marijuana extract remained good corrosion inhibitor in several corrosion measuring techniques used in previous research.

CONCLUSION

This review research work summaries results of various author on cannabis extracts as corrosion inhibitors. And the different result prove that cannabis sativa leaves extract can mitigate corrosion in acidic media and other corrosive environment not only for mild steel but other metals. It is reliable and eco-friendly inhibitor. It will help researchers and inhibitors user and marketer to know about marijuana inhibitive performance on metals in corrosive environments

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The effect of combining cannabis sativa with other plants inhibitors can be investigated.
- ii. The inhibition efficiency of the extract can be tested in crude oil, concrete, soil etc.
- iii. The inhibiting action of the extracts at higher temperatures could be investigated.

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